

SOME TOUCHES ON CONFIGURATION OF IDIOMATIC EXPRESSIONS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract

As has shown recent linguistic research in the field of idiomaticity, both the synthetic and the morphological pattern of an idiom may undergo a considerable change on contextual appropriateness: idioms displaced from one surrounding to another assume new distributive capacities and undergo interesting lexical and grammatical (morphological and syntactic) changes.

Particularly, the article touches upon one of the lexical variables of idiomatic expressions- *ellipsis and insertion*. In the framework of this research firstly, has been established a close relationship between the idioms and the particular *determining* context in which they appear and secondly, goes insights the process of transformation that the idioms undergo in certain contexts.

Keywords: variables, invariable, lexical changes, ellipsis, insertion, determining context

All natural human languages possess a great variety of multi-word units designed as idioms in which the globality nomination reigns supreme over the structural separability of the whole. Idioms are to great extent a product of culture. As a manifestation of the national wit, as a particular sort of national creativity, idioms through the system images, symbols, and stereotypes fixed in them carry on from generation to generation the accumulated culture and, thus ensure national identity. Being in fact, institutionalized metaphors or similes they come into being on the basis of the specific worldview over a particular speech community and reflect its empirical, historical, and spiritual experience.

There is not clear-out definition of idioms. Even amongst scholars, it is difficult to find what precisely is or is not an idiom, because of the diversity of the class and the multiplicity of generalized definitions that fail to convey their actual characteristics. It is mainly defined as a complex item that is longer than word-form but shorter than a sentence and each constituent part in idiom patterning does not contribute to the overall meaning of the phrase. The reason for this semantic anomaly derives mainly from the fact that an idiom is not built up word by word according to the grammar of the language, but is a non-compositional phrase that is learned, stored, and recycled as a single chunk.

Perhaps the most exhaustive definition of an idiom is presented by Raymond Gibbs: "By the term idiom, the speaker should learn "dead" metaphors and speech gambits by arbitrarily pairing each phrase some non-literal meaning without any awareness of why these phrases mean what they do" (1994,695).

M. Baker states that idioms are "frozen patterns of language which allow little or no variation in form and often carry meaning which cannot be deduced from their individual components" (1992, 63).

If we try to make some generalizations, the following features of idioms in their functioning become apparent:

1. Idioms facilitate communication.
2. Idioms contain more meaning.
3. Idioms convey speaker commitment and evaluation.
4. Idioms provide textual coherence.

It's a well- acknowledged fact that an idiom denotes an expression unique to a language, especially one whose sense is not predictable from the meaning and arrangement of its elements.

However, idioms undergo certain changes in a particular discourse situation.

Before speaking about the transformation that the idioms undergo in certain contexts, we should first of all find out what term is adequate for the particular changes that idioms undergo in an appropriate discourse situation. The phenomenon of idiomatic changes is termed differently by linguistic schools. In linguistics the terms "deformation", "degradation", the term "transformation" are coined for this purpose.

Deformation and degradation are viewed as two parallel phenomena.

Deformation of idioms is usually defined in linguistics as a figure of speech that destroys the idiomatic stability of the phrase and awakens its constituent parts by using them as separate units.

Deformation is the modification of various idiomatic units, which comprises in itself synthetic transformation of idioms, their inversions, contextual synonymic and antonymic equivalents of idioms, as well as expansion of idioms and their components via a set of elementary devices.

Degradation is the certain changes within the idioms as a result of which both literal and figurative meanings of idiomatic units are retained. As a result of degradation an idiomatic unit generally "breaks into pieces" and begins to function as a free word combination.

A thorough study of these two phenomena shows that the former notion of *deformation and degradation* are two chains of the same process and the latter is the logical continuation of the first one.

The term "transformation" comes from late Middle English: from Old French, or from Late Latin word *transformationem*, noun of the verb *transformare* meaning "Change the shape or form of".

The term "transformation" can be defined in linguistics, as a process of profound and radical change that orients a phrase in a new direction and takes it to an entirely different level of effectiveness. In other

words, it's a process by which an element in the underlying logical deep structure of a sentence is converted to an element in the surface structure. Transformation implies a basic change of character and little or no resemblance with the past configuration or structure. The term "transformation" much more nicely works into the process as it reveals the changes within the frame of idiomatic expression. However, transformation touches upon formal changes; the composition of idiomatic phrase changes whereas the meaning remains unaltered.

However, our analysis has shown that idioms undergo certain changes of metaphoric nature in a particular context and as a result of which the literal and figurative meaning of the components of idioms are brought back to life to make a new metaphor. Therefore, we propose the term "**variability**" for the changes that the idioms undergo in the appropriate discourse situation. In a flourishing context idioms may undergo structural and semantic changes. The author manipulates with the idioms making the situation or event described in the text more vivid and emphatic and in each context a new "variable" of an idiom comes to life which turns the text from stylistically neutral into a stylistically marked one. Many linguists claim that idioms are comparatively stable and semantically inseparable units. However, recent linguistic research in the field of idiomaticity has shown that figurative expressions are not completely frozen and usually allow certain structural variability in particular contexts. In fact, not all idioms allow variability, but the majority of them are changeable to a certain degree. The data at our disposal show that some idioms allow various kinds of lexical and grammatical variation, some to a higher and others to the less degree. We can find a straightforward connection between the transparency and stability of idioms: idiomatic collocations are more transparent than idiomatic unities, whereas opaque word-groups are completely non-transparent. Hence, idiomatic collocations are the most flexible ones in a particular discourse situation and can easily undergo the process of variability bringing to life different variables of the same idiom.

A thorough analysis establishes a clear picture of the involvement of idioms in the discourse situation and reveals the subtle semantic and structural interrelations between the contextual and base components on the one hand and on the other hand the interaction with other elements of the text.

Although structurally idioms are polylexemic compositions, semantically they represent one unit of meaning. The majority of such units has figurative transferred meaning and is based on the semantic relationship of metaphor. The metaphoric nature of an idiom accounts for its idiomaticity and results in the unpredictability of the global meaning of the whole from the literal meanings of the constituent parts. Sustainable development of an idiom is due to the associative links of the image-bearing components of the base form and the newly-formed sub-images. The network of sub-images creates metaphoric space. The instantial extension of the base metaphor provides semantic and stylistic interpretation of the context.

Literary discourse is relevant for writers who find plenty of possibilities to transform idioms both lexically and grammatically. The author manipulates with the components of the idiom making them serve his or her purpose. The events and concepts which are being talked about in particular context also affect the appropriate choice of idiom. In other words, a close relationship has been established between the idioms and the metaphoric comprehension of a particular context. When these two aspects of the speech event match the use of an idiom is represented as appropriate in the particular discourse situation. We define such type of context as "*determining*". This context is determined by two factors: by internal factors of the given linguistic context and by external factors – specific frames of cultural reference.

In passing from general usage into some special sphere of communications, an idiom, as a rule, undergoes some sort of *lexical changes*. *Deletion* is one of lexical variables, when one of the lexical items is replaced by another one and the substitution of the variable member doesn't destroy the set expression as such. By variable element we mean the element of the idiomatic expression which is structurally necessary, but free to vary lexically (Arnold, 1973:148).

The process of *deletion* is natural for all spheres of the language, but in different spheres different terms are used to define this phenomenon: ellipsis, elision, contraction, abbreviation, etc. In the sphere of idioms the term "*ellipsis*" is used to the phenomenon when a part of an idiom functions as a complete form of an idiom.

There are some cases in the English language when parts of idioms are used so often that they gradually become as if separate idioms. The idioms *red herring* (something that distracts attention from important things) and *rolling stone* (a person who is not steady) once used as *to draw/trail a red herring across the track/path* (to do something that would distract a person from important things) and *a rolling stone gathers no moss* (a person who is not steady does not do well in life) today can easily function in the language in their short forms.

Besides this type of ellipsis having an independent status in the language, there exist another kind of deletion – an ellipsis that functions only in a particular situation or discourse as a context – driven unit. Ellipsis that occurs in particular context is used for stylistic purposes in the literary text. Let us consider the following examples:

In England and France he was the square peg in the round hole, but here the holes were any sort of shape, and no sort of peg was quite amiss. (W. S. Maugham, 11)

"Sooner or later he'll be quite ready to come back to London, and no great harm will have been done." "I wouldn't do that," said Mrs. MacAndrew. "I'd give him all the rope he wants. He'll come back with his tail between his legs and settle down again quite comfortably. (W. S. Maugham, 18)

The first example presents only separate elements (in the second part of the sentence) of the idiom *a square peg in a round hole* (= a person unsuitable for

the position he fills). The second example is more interesting, for it pertains only one word from the original sample. The word “rope” represents the idiom *to give somebody enough rope to hang himself* (allow somebody enough freedom of action in the expectation that one will overreach oneself).

In the next example ellipsis gives a new semantically independent status to a former component of an idiom (skeleton) in the idiom “*a/the skeleton in the cupboard*”.

“*Oh! I don't think I'm denying the importance of the biographical element in literary appreciation. I know very well how much a full knowledge of a writer's life adds to the interpretation of the work. I am not inclined to expose skeletons which have been so carefully buried*”. (W. S. Maugham, 177)

The ellipsis of idioms is quite a problematic issue, for one must know the language very well in order to grasp the full meaning of the idiom from only the constituent part of it. For the native speakers of English, the process of deletions in idioms is not as problematic as it is for those who speak English as a second language only. A non-native speaker must have a “linguistic sense” to recognize and fully understand the omitted constituents of idioms.

The opposite process of ellipsis is **insertion**.

Insertions (also known as *additions*) are considered to be all the extraneous lexical elements, which do not appear in the original form of the idiom. Normally insertions are not allowed within the structure of idioms, but especially in literature, they are used rather often. The insertions to the idioms are usually adjectives and adverbs, which intensify the meaning of the idiom.

Breaking syntactic closeness and integrity of idioms, a writer includes into narrative speech separate components of expressions which however don't lose connection with content and structure of the whole stable combination.

E.g. **hold (keep/put) one's nose to the grindstone** - to work hard and constantly.

I can see as far into a grindstone as another man; further than a good many, perhaps, because I had my nose well kept to it when I was young (Ch. Dickens. Hard Times)

to be a shadow of one's former self - a smaller, weaker, or less important form of someone or something

He was worn by anxiety and remorse almost to a shadow... (Ch. Dickens. Oliver Twist).

Lord Augustus: I want to speak to you particularly, dear boy, I'm worn to a shadow (O. Wilde. Lady Windermere's Fan).

As we see in these examples, writers can differently change the structure of idioms depending on stylistic effect they aim to achieve.

In case of insertion the sequence of component parts may be broken and some additional elements or words may be inserted without destroying the idiomatic meaning of the phrase and establishing syntactic ties with its constant elements. For instance: “*Were they on very friendly terms?*” “Not specially, I should say. Not that I knew anyway.” (W. S. Maugham, 9)

The above-presented example shows the case of

insertion within the idiom. The original idiom is *to be on friendly terms* (to keep good relationship) and the insertion of the word “*very*” enhances the meaning of the idiom, which can be paraphrased as “to keep especially good relationship”.

flesh and blood – a living human body, especially with reference to its natural limitations; a human being; the quality of being alive; one's own relatives in reality

I suppose that little writer chap hasn't suddenly gone off his onion and decided to do one of his crimes in flesh instead of on paper? (A. Christie Death in the Clouds, p. 91)

In the above presented sentence we can come across the elliptical use of the idiom “*flesh and blood*”. The lexical item “*flesh*” in this example stands for the idiom, which has the meaning “*a living human body*”. However, the insertion of the preposition “*in*” changes the meaning of the idiom. In this case the idiom refers to reality, since the phrase *in “flesh” has gained the meaning “in reality”*.

As we have stated above when we try to interpret idioms we need to be familiar with some specific frames of cultural reference since without the suitable cultural knowledge our interpretation of meaning becomes a texting procedure.

Hence, an idiom's semantics can be also influenced by national colouring. The phrase “the salt of the earth” derives from the Bible, Matthew 5:13 and means “those of great worth and reliability”.

“Ye are the salt of the earth” but if the salt have lost his savour, wherewith shall it be salted? It is thenceforth good for nothing, but to be cast out, and to be trodden under foot of men.”

The positivity towards salt in this phrase conflicts with many other uses of the *word salt in English*, which has also been used to express negative concepts: for example, in the Middle Ages, salt was spread on land to poison it, as a punishment to landowners who had transgressed against society in some way. It seems that the “excellent” meaning in ‘the salt of the earth’ was coined in reference to the value of salt. This is reflected in other old phrases too, for example, the aristocratic and powerful of the earth were ‘above the salt’ and valued workers were ‘worth their salt’. It is interesting to note the cultural differences of the perception of salt in English differs on the one hand, from Hebrew and from Armenian on the other hand. Both for us and Jews, like other Eastern nations, the salt is the symbol of prosperity and does not possess any negative sense. Another interesting aspect of this idiom is the slight difference of its meaning in English and other languages. In Russian and other post-sovetic nations, for example, this idiom is used to denote the aristocratic layer of the society, the intelligent and educated people. This is due to their belief that it's the intelligent people who are the most important, and on whom the world's progress depends. In English, the perception of human importance is otherwise. In England, it is the peasants, common workers and common people who are considered to be the basis of society and without whom aristocrats cannot live, that's why in English the *salt of the earth* denotes mostly poor working men and women.

Another idiom of cultural markedness is “*to cast*

pearl before swine". It is well known the attitude of some nations towards *pigs and pork*. This idiom bears that very negative meaning of the word *pig* which is not so actual neither in Armenian nor English, as we both have more or less tolerant attitude towards swine. In spite of the absence of that very symbolic meaning of unsacredness in our languages, this idiom has firmly entered the common vocabulary of both languages. It is interesting to note the cross references of this idiom, where the *swine* is sometimes replaced by the "fool", "dog" or other expressions.

As we see in these examples, writers can differently change the structure of an idiomatic expression depending on the effect they aim to achieve.

To sum up, idiomatic variability strongly correlates with invariability. At paradigmatic level an invariant works whereas at syntagmatic level variables come to life. Invariant is a constant stable unit in contrast to variables that are context-driven.

Discourse and idioms are interwoven and in an appropriate discourse situation idioms undergo considerable changes not only in their meaning but also on their semantics. Both the synthetic and the morphological pattern of an idiom may undergo a considerable change on contextual appropriateness. A worn-out metaphor may come to life again because of dynamic relevance. Methods of meanings of constituent elements of idiomatic expressions are rather specific for every creative

writer.

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